

İZOTERMAL KONTURLARIN DENEYSEL ÖLÇÜMLERLE TESPİTİ

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Özet

Sıcaklık profilini görsellemek için çizilen izotermal kontur çizgileri şimdiye kadar ısı yayılım denklemlerinin analitik ya da numerik çözümlerinden teorik olarak türetilmiştir. Bu çalışmada doğrudan sıcaklık ölçümleri temel alınarak sıcaklık profili bulunması denenmiştir. Bunun için silindirik bir kapta katılaştan metalin sekiz farklı konumuna termokupullar yerleştirilmiş ve her saniye sıcaklıklar kaydedilmiştir. Azimütal simetrik silindirik koordinatlarda sıcaklık yarıçap (r), yükseklik (z) ve zaman (t) değişkenlerinin fonksiyonu olarak ($T(r,z,t)$) tayin edilmiş ve bu fonksiyonun aşağıdaki polinom ile yaklaşık modelleneceği varsayılmıştır.

$$T(r, z, t) = w_{00}(t) + w_{01}(t)z + w_{20}(t)r^2 + w_{02}(t)z^2 + w_{40}(t)r^4 + w_{21}(t)r^2z + w_{03}(t)z^3 + w_{22}(t)r^2z^2$$

Sekiz farklı (r,z) konumları ve bu konumlardaki $T(r,z,t)$ değerleri ölçüm ile bilindiğinden, yukarıdaki denklemde görülen sekiz zamana bağlı bilinmeyen fonksiyon (w_{00}, w_{01}, \dots) lineer cebir ile bulunmuştur. En son elde edilen sıcaklık fonksiyonu olan $T(r,z,t)$ belirli sıcaklık değerlerine eşitlenerek, eş sıcaklık eğrileri elde edilmiştir.

Anahtar kelimeler: izotermal eğriler, eş-sıcaklık yüzeyleri, sıcaklık profili

DETERMINATION OF ISOTHERMAL CONTOURS BY EXPERIMENTAL MEASUREMENTS

Abstract

The isothermal contour lines drawn to visualize the temperature profile have so far been theoretically derived from analytical or numerical solutions of the heat transfer equations. In this study, it has been tried to find a temperature profile based on direct temperature measurements. For this, thermocouples were placed in eight different positions of the metal solidified in a cylindrical container and the temperatures were recorded every second. In azimuthal symmetrical cylindrical coordinates, the temperature is determined as a function of the radius (r), height (z) and time (t) variables ($T(r,z,t)$) and it is assumed that this function will be modeled approximately with the following polynomial.

$$T(r, z, t) = w_{00}(t) + w_{01}(t)z + w_{20}(t)r^2 + w_{02}(t)z^2 + w_{40}(t)r^4 + w_{21}(t)r^2z + w_{03}(t)z^3 + w_{22}(t)r^2z^2$$

Since eight different (r,z) positions and $T(r,z,t)$ values at these positions are known by measurement, eight time dependent unknown functions ($w_{00}, w_{0j}..$) seen in the above equation were found by linear algebra. By equating $T(r,z,t)$ which is the last obtained temperature function to certain temperature values, isotherm curves are obtained.

Keywords: isothermal curves, isothermal surfaces, temperature profile

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